

An Exploration of Mathematical Principles of Musical Temperaments: A Case Study of Why the 12-equal-temperament Is Dominant

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ABSTRACT

Most teen students are simply taught how to play instruments during middle or high school rather than being explained the basic mathematical principles behind the musical temperaments or musical terms like notes, chords, scales, dominant 7th, harmonics, major, minor, and so on. This tends to lead to confusion and frustration. In this article, the mathematical principles are interpreted in an easy-to-understand way to illustrate that the ultimate goal of music is to satisfy the human ear. It is a compromised result of how music originated, evolved, and developed given the physical constraint of human audibility and fundamental sound theory as well as the music-developing trends and demands. By comparing and contrasting the 4 major music temperaments: the Pythagorean tuning, the just intonation, the 1/4 comma meantone, and the 12-equal-temperament in mathematical methods, the article concludes why the 12-equal-temperament is dominant nowadays.

Keywords: Music temperament, Perfect Fifth, Just Intonation, Equal Temperament, Pitches, Frequencies, Mathematical Principle.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dating back 9,000 years ago, a bone flute found in Jiahu, Henan province, China, was known as the oldest musical instrument in China. Since 1984, six complete bone flutes, as well as the fragments of at least thirty more, have been excavated from several early Neolithic Jiahu culture tombs in Jiahu, Wuyuan County, Henan Province, in Central China (Wenwu, 1989).

Our ancestors were able to play musical instruments. We have less knowledge of what kind of music they could produce but we do know that the 8-hole bone flute can

produce the “all harmonics and two registers” (Lee, 1999). People at that time should have been far away from the establishment of sound theory as well as mathematics was at a very premature stage. It can be inferred that ancient people were able to grasp the basic music skills to play harmony primarily based on daily observations and practices.

In the Pythagorean age, people found that a big hammer and a small hammer could generate harmonic sound if the weight of the big hammer is at a certain whole number relationship to that of the small hammer (Murray, 1951). This encouraged artisans to understand the general laws on consonance and beat rates. In China, people developed the “rule of the third” method (孙济南、周柱铨, 2000), a method by which more pitches were obtained by shortening the distance as $\frac{2}{3}$ of the original length or by extending the distance as $\frac{4}{3}$ of the original length. By repeating this method, artisans could obtain quite several pitches to use for the performance.

Figure 1: What Frequency is vs What Human Ear Perceives

The mathematical theory of sound propagation began with Isaac Newton (1642-1727), whose Principia (1686) included a mechanical interpretation of sound as being "pressure" pulses transmitted through neighboring fluid particles (O'Neill,

2017). That wave theory of sound illustrates mathematically why only if the frequency between the tonic and their overtones at certain whole number relationships can generate the harmonic sounds. The frequency is also known as “the pitch”. The consonance is defined and measured by the compatibility and the perception of harmony that the human ear and brain can perceive (Norrback, 2020). For instance, the pattern of waves with frequencies at 50 Hz (Figure 1), 100 Hz, and 200 Hz sounds much better than that of 50 Hz, 100 Hz, and 150 Hz. In addition, it was revealed that the human ear can only perceive frequencies in the range of 20 Hz ~ 20,000 Hz (Sethares, 2009). Beyond that, humans cannot perceive sounds while some other animals can do a better job than humans. Bats, whales, and penguins can send and receive ultrasounds (Barker, 1989). The human ear and brain are much more sensitive to the relationships of the frequencies between two or more sounds. That being said, even though there could be some harmonic pitches, given the physical constraints of the human ear and brain, those pitches would not be considered during the music composing and performing.

There were and are thousands of various music tuning methods being introduced, developed, and discarded over a long historical period across different geographical locations (Ledbetter, 2002). Pythagorean tuning was known as the earliest music temperament in Europe. At that time, it was commonly accepted that rational numbers dominated the world, which explains why the Pythagorean tuning was based on the fifth while trying to use rational numbers to tune musical instruments (Plamondon, 2009). Later on, since there was some dissonance in Pythagorean tuning, people tried to discover more harmonic pitches. This was the driving force to introduce the just intonation tuning method (Johnston, 2006) which can fix many dissonance problems of Pythagorean tuning. From the Renaissance to the Baroque period, the major third was very popular. As a matter of result, musicians and theorists started to find better ways to preserve the perfection of the major third, one of the significant temperaments was 1/4 comma meantone (Lindley, 1990) which greatly compromised the major third and the fifth. During Johann S. Bach’s time, transposition was highly preferred and required that the music be easily transposed from one key signature to another for better performance and expression (Kelletat, 1981). To satisfy that demand, the well-tempered music temperament was widely accepted, as a matter of result, the 12-equal-temperament (Barbour, 1951) stepped up to the center of the stage and has been dominating through nowadays.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim of the Study

There are and were quite a great number of tuning methods introduced and developed over time to build different systems of music sounds across different geographical regions during different historical periods. The fifth is the fundamental interval in many temperaments. In general, all of the various temperaments could be categorized into 3 buckets: open temperaments, closed unequal temperaments, and equal temperaments.

The article below will explore the 4 typical temperaments to discover the relationship between mathematics and music.

2.2 Research Design

The research of this study is designed to take 5 steps to analyze the most acceptable tuning method:

Step 1 - Tune a keyboard musical instrument with the 4 tuning methods respectively.

Step 2 - Collect the data set of the frequency ratio from each of the 4 experiments.

Step 3 - Sort out the minimum value of the frequencies for the first 3 experiments.

Step 4 - Compare and analyze the frequency from the 4th experiment against the minimum value from step 3.

Step 5 - Analyze the deviations by calculating the rate of the average error to find out the most satisfactory temperament method.

2.3 Data Collection

2.3.1 Experiment 1 - Pythagorean Tuning

Pythagorean temperament was known historically as the first of temperaments in Europe. This temperament uses the fifth as the building block and tries to make all fifths perfect while preserving the perfect octaves as well. Pythagorean temperament is a typical open temperament, as all fifths but one are perfect, and the last one is dissonant.

Figure 2: The frequency difference caused by the Pythagorean and the Perfect fifth

Tuning is not very difficult since the perfect fifth is the second-simplest interval with the frequency at ratio 3:2. Starting from C_4 (Figure 2), one can get G_4 by moving up 5 steps by moving up while obtaining F_3 by moving down 5 steps to the left. By repeating this method, one can tune all 12 semitones, however within 7 different octaves, from D_1^b to $C_8^\#$. This requires a total of 12 steps, up and down. After that, all notes within all octaves can be obtained by building the octave intervals from already tuned 12 semitones.

Below are the steps of how to obtain the whole octave from C_4 to B_4 :

1. Set $C_4 = 1$ as the benchmark
2. $G_4 = C_4 \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3}{2}$
3. $D_5 = G_4 \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{9}{4}$
4. Lower D_5 one octave to get $D_4 = \frac{9}{4} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{9}{8}$

5. $A_4 = D_4 \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{27}{16}$

6. $E_5 = A_4 \times \frac{3}{2} = \frac{81}{32}$

7. Lower E_5 one octave to get $E_4 = \frac{81}{32} \times \frac{1}{2} = \frac{81}{64}$

8. Lower C_4 one octave to get $F_3 = 1 / (3/2) = \frac{2}{3}$

9. Double F_3 one octave to get $F_4 = \frac{2}{3} \times 2 = \frac{4}{3}$

10. $B_3^b = F_4 / (3/2) = \frac{4}{3} \times \frac{2}{3} = \frac{8}{9}$

11. Double B_3^b one octave to get $B_4^b = B_3^b \times 2 = \frac{8}{9} \times 2 = \frac{16}{9}$

With this method, all twelve semitones in between $C_4 - C_5$ will be obtained as below:

C_4	D_4	E_4	F_4	G_4	A_4	B_4
1	9/8	81/64	4/3	3/2	27/16	243/128
D_4^b	E_4^b	$F_4^\#$	G_4^b	A_4^b	B_4^b	C_5
256/243	32/27	729/512	1024/729	128/81	16/9	2

From the above table, the $F_4^\#$ isn't the same as G_4^b because of $\frac{729}{512} \neq \frac{1024}{729}$. Comparing the 2 notes, we have to drop the frequency of G_4^b in order to get the adjacent notes harmonic. A similar case can be applied to other notes like $C_4^\#$ and D_4^b , only D_4^b is kept to obtain the consonance though the names of the notes are still being used today. This fairly well explains why a certain flat music scale is not the same as the sharp scale of its preceding note. Ex. $F^\#$ scale is not the same as G^b scale. This is also the reason why eventually 12 semitones dominate other than 19 semitones within one octave as people have to compromise between the more usable notes and the harmonic intervals they can produce.

The significance of the Pythagorean Tuning method is that it tries to find a way to compromise the octave and the fifth. The problem with the Pythagorean temperament is that the frequency ratio between D_1^b to $C_8^\#$ equals $(\frac{3}{2})^{12} = 129.75$, which differs from the ratio $2^7 = 128$ that should be between the notes differing by 7 octaves. That

said, tuning a perfect fifth is incompatible with tuning perfect octaves. This temperament is relatively good for a single musical instrument to play. As tuning perfect octaves is a priority, one has to sacrifice one of the fifths. For instance, if one changes the frequency of $C_8^\#$ by tuning it in a perfect 7-octave interval with D_1^b , then the fifth of $F_7^\# - C_8^\#$ will sound horrible and not usable in music. The disadvantage of Pythagorean temperament is that there are not too many music scales besides C available for use as the dissonance of sounds will occur.

2.3.2 Experiment 2 – Just Intonation Tuning

The $E_4 = \frac{81}{64}$ is relatively less harmonic, but it is very close to $\frac{5}{4}$ as the error of distance is approximately as:

$$\frac{\frac{81}{64} - \frac{5}{4}}{\frac{81}{64}} \times 100\% \approx \frac{1}{81} \times 100\% \approx 1.23\%$$

This tells explicitly that the difference between $\frac{81}{64}$ and $\frac{5}{4}$ is $\frac{1}{81}$. In another way, the ratio of $\frac{5}{4}$ and $\frac{81}{64}$ is $\frac{81}{80}$ called a syntonic comma, which illustrates the deviation from Pythagorean tuning to Just Intonation Major Third. If slightly changed E_4 to $\frac{5}{4}$, it works more harmonically with C_4 and G_4 as:

C_4	E_4	G_4
1	81/64	3/2
C_4	E_4	G_4
1	5/4	3/2

This comes the just major third.

Just intonation is the tuning method that uses the regular number harmonics of a single fundamental frequency. Compared to the Pythagorean method, whose tones far from the C scale will generate the horror sound, the just intonation is much more harmonic. This method was brought up in the 1700s age by mathematicians and musical theorists like Alexander Malcon. By introducing the regular number, the ratio of just intonation looks much more precise than Pythagorean from a mathematical perspective. The importance of just intonation is to find as many harmonic tones as

possible and try to preserve the major third perfect along with octaves.

However, there are whole major thirds and minor thirds in just intonation. For the whole major third, $C : E : G = 1 : \frac{5}{4} : \frac{3}{2} = 4 : 5 : 6$, the minor major third, $C : E^b : G = 1 : \frac{6}{5} : \frac{3}{2} = 10 : 12 : 15$. With this method, one can obtain the rest of the other notes within one octave.

C_4	D_4	E_4	F_4	G_4	A_4	B_4
1	$\frac{9}{8}$	$\frac{5}{4}$	$\frac{4}{3}$	$\frac{3}{2}$	$\frac{5}{3}$	$\frac{15}{8}$
D_4^b	E_4^b	$F_4^\#$	G_4^b	A_4^b	B_4^b	C_5
$\frac{16}{15}$	$\frac{6}{5}$	$\frac{45}{32}$	$\frac{36}{25}$	$\frac{8}{5}$	$\frac{9}{5}$	2

Just intonation was very popular in the Renaissance and early Baroque periods as the major third and the minor third work very well in choral and orchestral performance. However, several disadvantages were revealed that were caused by the major thirds and the minor thirds. For example:

$\frac{D}{C} = \frac{G}{F} = \frac{B}{A} = \frac{9}{8}$ while $\frac{E}{D} = \frac{A}{G} = \frac{10}{9}$, since $\frac{9}{8} > \frac{10}{9}$, there is a difference among whole notes. In addition, $\frac{F}{E} = \frac{C}{B} = \frac{16}{15}$ is larger than the fifth.

$\frac{A}{D} = \frac{5}{3} \div \frac{9}{8} = \frac{40}{27}$ is smaller than the fifth. There are also some notes not harmonic and have to be discarded. As a matter of result, only 12 semitones were retained.

2.3.3 Experiment 3 – 1/4 Comma Meantone Tuning

Western common practice music usually cannot be played in just intonation but requires a systematic tuning scale given the confusion brought by the major thirds and the minor thirds. The tuning can involve either the irregularities of good temperament or be constructed as a regular temperament, either some form of equal temperament or some other regular meantone, but in all cases, it will involve the fundamental features of the meantone temperament. For example, the root of the chord D_4 , if tuned to a fifth above the dominant, it would be a major whole tone $\frac{9}{8}$ above the tonic. If tuned a just minor third $\frac{6}{5}$ below a just subdominant degree of $\frac{4}{3}$, however, the interval

from the tonic would equal a minor whole tone $\frac{10}{9}$. Meantone temperament reduces the difference between $\frac{9}{8}$ and $\frac{10}{9}$. Their ratio, $\frac{9}{8} \div \frac{10}{9} = \frac{81}{80}$, is treated as a unison. The distance $\frac{81}{80}$ called the syntonic comma, is the key comma of meantone tuning. With the 1/4 comma meantone tuning method, the frequency of G_4 will be transposed to: $\frac{3}{2} \div (\frac{81}{80})^{\frac{1}{4}} = (5)^{\frac{1}{4}} = 1.49534$.

In quarter-comma meantone tuning, where a just major third (5:4) is required, a slightly narrower distance is obtained by stacking 4 fifths while minus two octaves can get a major third. The example is $D_4 - D_5 - D_6 - F_6^\#$ in our experiment.

All 12 semitones can be constructed by starting from a given base note and increasing or decreasing its frequency by one or more fifths. In our experiment, we start from C_4 . The construction table below illustrates how the pitches of the notes are obtained with concerning C_4 as the base note. For each note in the basic octave, the table provides the conventional name of the interval from C_4 to C_5 , and the formula to compute its frequency ratio. In the table below, we set $c = \frac{3}{2} \div (\frac{81}{80})^{\frac{1}{4}}$ or $(5)^{\frac{1}{4}}$.

C_4	D_4	E_4	F_4	G_4	A_4	B_4
1	$c^2 \times 2^{-1}$	$c^4 \times 2^{-2}$	$c^6 \times 2^{-3}$	$c^1 \times 2^0$	$c^3 \times 2^{-1}$	$c^5 \times 2^{-2}$
D_4^b	E_4^b	$F_4^\#$	G_4^b	A_4^b	B_4^b	C_5
$c^{-5} \times 2^3$	$c^{-3} \times 2^2$	$c^{-2} \times 2^1$	$c^{-6} \times 2^4$	$c^{-4} \times 2^3$	$c^{-2} \times 2^2$	2

The 1/4 comma semitone was designed to compromise the third and the fifth. It is also part of the equal temperament family. However, it involves a lot of mathematical skills and some variations slightly tune each small interval into a different ratio which makes it hard to establish a common standard.

2.3.4 Experiment 4 – 12-Equal-Temperament Tuning

The well-tempered tuning is slightly different from the one that is now widely used: 12-equal-temperament that is fully mathematically equal. It should be noted that the 12-equal-temperament was brought up much earlier than Bach’s time but it was not until Bach’s age it was widely accepted and started dominating. Even though it was not Bach who invented the 12-equal-temperaments, Bach did a lot to promote this tuning method. Below we will discuss the tuning method of 12-equal-temperaments.

It is very easy to obtain the 12 semitones using the 12-equal-temperament. Starting from one base note, with a ratio of $\sqrt[12]{2} : 1$, we can obtain the next pitch. In our experiment, we start from C_4 to get the full set of the semitones from C_4 to C_5 as below:

C_4	D_4	E_4	F_4	G_4	A_4	B_4
1	$2^{\frac{2}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{4}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{6}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{7}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{9}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{11}{12}}$
D_4^b	E_4^b	$F_4^\#$	G_4^b	A_4^b	B_4^b	C_5
$2^{\frac{1}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{3}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{5}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{5}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{8}{12}}$	$2^{\frac{10}{12}}$	2

2.4 Data Analysis

By far, we have obtained the frequencies with 4 experiments. We summarize the data for the first 3 experiments in the below table, with each of the interval names, the frequency for each of the tuning methods as well as the minimum value of the frequency. The minimum value will be used to compare against the one being generated from 12-equal-temperament.

Interval Name	Frequency ratio of tuning methods			Minimum frequency
	Pythagorean	Just Intonation	1/4 comma-meantone	
C - Unison	1	1	1	1
D^b - Minor second	$\frac{256}{243} = 1.06787$	$\frac{16}{15} = 1.06666$	1.05626	1.05626
D – Major second	$\frac{9}{8} = 1.125$	$\frac{9}{8} = 1.125$	1.12014	1.12014
E^b - Minor third	$\frac{32}{27} = 1.18519$	$\frac{6}{5} = 1.2$	1.18553	1.18519
E – Major third	$\frac{81}{64} = 1.26563$	$\frac{5}{4} = 1.25$	1.26077	1.25

We compare the 12-equal-temperament against the minimum value of the frequency from the other 3 experiments as below:

Interval Name	12-equal-temperament	Minimum frequency	The error of distance (%)
C - Unison	$2^0 = 1$	1	0
D^b - Minor second	$2^{\frac{1}{12}} = 1.05946$	1.05625	0.30%
D – Major second	$2^{\frac{2}{12}} = 1.12246$	1.12014	0.21%
E^b - Minor third	$2^{\frac{3}{12}} = 1.18921$	1.18519	0.34%
E – Major third	$2^{\frac{4}{12}} = 1.25992$	1.25	0.79%
F - Fourth	$2^{\frac{5}{12}} = 1.33484$	1.33333	0.11%
$F^\#$ - Diminished fifth	$2^{\frac{6}{12}} = 1.41421$	1.40625	0.38%
G - fifth	$2^{\frac{7}{12}} = 1.49831$	1.49534	0.20%
A^b - Minor sixth	$2^{\frac{8}{12}} = 1.58740$	1.58025	0.45%
A – Major sixth	$2^{\frac{9}{12}} = 1.68179$	1.66667	0.90%
B^b - Minor seventh	$2^{\frac{10}{12}} = 1.78179$	1.77778	0.23%
B – Major seventh	$2^{\frac{11}{12}} = 1.88775$	1.875	0.68%
C - Octave	2	2	0

The above table, explicitly illustrates that the 12-equal-temperament is very close to each of the minimum values. That is, each of the frequencies is slightly different from what is ideally harmonic. However, since the 12-equal-temperament greatly facilitates the musicians to transpose the music from one key to another, which is driven by the current music composing trends and market demands, it eventually became the dominating music temperament.

3. RESULTS

The music temperament has been evolving during different historical periods across various geographical areas. The driving force for the development of music temperament is the striving for consonance under the trade-off of the constraints of the human ear and brain, the usable pitches, and the harmonizations they appear, and the music preferences over various geographical locations historically.

From the above 4 experiments, we can conclude and summarize below:

- Pythagorean tuning was designed to compromise the fifth and the octave
- Just Intonation tuning was designed to compromise the major third and the octave
- 1/4 comma meantone was designed to compromise the fifth and the major third
- 12-equal-temperament was designed to enable transposition by slightly sacrificing harmonic of each of the 12 pitches

4. DISCUSSION

There are thousands of different music temperaments or tuning methods all over the globe. In China, Zhu Zaiyu was the one who initially came up with the 12-equal-temperament (杨传中, 2003). However, it was not widely adopted as most musicians did not believe it necessary to follow that rule while playing. In addition, the musical instruments at that time did not require that kind of musical temperament. A similar case can be found in Europe when the 12-equal-temperament was designed, it was not fully accepted by the musicians and theorists until Bach's age when the transposition was a top priority. In India and other places like the Middle East, there were other types of music temperaments based on people's preferences and the characteristics of their local musical instruments (Daniélou, 1968).

5. CONCLUSION

Music temperaments are what musicians and theorists summarized throughout the daily operation and practice over a long historical period across various geographical areas. The intention to find the best tuning method is to satisfy the need for music appreciation over different periods during which people's preferences were various. It is a long period of exploration for musicians to obtain usable pitches while trying to preserve the perfect between the fifth and the octave, the major third and the octave, the fifth and the major third, and enabling the transpositions. A lot of compromises have been made during the long evolving process.

It has been proved historically and practically that the 12 semitones with 7 whole tones and 5 halftones are the most acceptable pattern of pitches regardless using whichever tuning methods like Pythagorean, Just Intonation, 1/4 comma semitones or 12-equal-temperament. Traditionally, the terms of musical scale are used in compliance with the fifth or just intonation regardless of the sign of the sharp and the flat though it may lead to confusion that a certain sharp and flat share the same key on the keyboard.

Interestingly, the international standard sets A = 440 Hz instead of C. This is because at that time the dominating music scale in Europe was key to A. To show respect to that practice, historically it is inherited and used nowadays. The key of C was much more popular later on, this is why nowadays the sequence of musical notes is defined in the format as C, D, E, F, G, A, and B.

It is a coincidence that music encountered mathematics. When music was developed and performed with various musical instruments, mathematics was still at its infant age and the knowledge of the mathematics that our ancestors grasped was very little. The development and evolution of music primarily relied on intuition from the human ear and brain. It was not until dating back 500 years or so from now that mathematics was used as an effective tool in measuring the music tuning to better guide the musicians and theorists to obtain more usable and harmonic pitches. One thing is sure, that perfect mathematics is not able to guarantee perfect pitches and harmonic tones. Mathematics is not the nature of the music but an effective tool for musicians and theorists to better model, design, and refine new music temperaments.

6. LIMITATION

A lot! The goal of this study is to illustrate the development and evolution of the music temperaments. We choose the 4 typical tuning methods and use them to come up with the frequencies and based on the results to compare against to conclude the justification why the 12-equal-temperaments succeeded and dominated.

There are a lot of tuning methods that were not well-covered. We break all of the music temperaments into 3 categories: open temperament, closed unequal temperament, and equal temperament. Inside each of these categories of the tuning methods, there are still many variations that are not well addressed.

One of the key driving forces for the development of music temperaments is musical expression. Musicians and theorists realized a long time ago that different keys or scales of music can express different “colors” or “emotions” (Barbour, 1951). For instance, the major scale is used to express joy and happiness while the minor scale is used to deliver depressed or sad emotions. To better express their feeling and experiences, different people in different areas composed and performed with different musical instruments. As a matter of result, they also introduced various music temperaments to achieve the above goal as needed. This is beyond the scope of the article and not addressed.

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